

A Prime-Factorization Invariant for Classifying Cyclic Privilege Escalation in Cloud IAM

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Abstract

Non-human identities (NHIs) in cloud environments may form strongly connected components (SCCs) that defeat existing automated policy analysis tools and require costly manual review. We introduce the primordial invariant: a canonical encoding of SCC cycle structure that enables automated classification of cyclic privilege patterns into three actionable categories: reduction (benign cycles that can be collapsed), fusion (structurally equivalent cycles that share a single analyst decision), and fusion-reduction (approximate variants that can be jointly reviewed and simplified).

Unlike attack-graph or black-box learning approaches, the method is lightweight, tolerant to bounded collisions, and designed explicitly for operational scalability rather than perfect discrimination.

Initial evidence of a live dataset sample suggests that the invariant compresses 297 observed privilege-cycle SCCs into 51 canonical signatures, a substantial reduction in the number of distinct SCCs requiring manual review.

1 Introduction

1.1 Evolution of Non-Human Identities in Cloud Infrastructure

Early non-human identities in enterprise environments were relatively static: long-lived service accounts bound to proprietary applications, executing a limited set of scheduled tasks with fixed permissions. Although rarely compliant with strict least-privilege principles, their behavior was predictable and amenable to manual auditing due to limited scope and infrequent change.

The adoption of Infrastructure as Code (IaC) and CI/CD orchestration has fundamentally altered this model. Contemporary non-human identities (NHIs), including CI/CD pipelines, automation frameworks, and cloud-native workload identities, now execute complex, multi-stage workflows that span heterogeneous services and environments. A single GitHub Actions workflow or Terraform pipeline may provision, configure, and validate multi-application stacks across development, staging, and production, dynamically acquiring and relinquishing permissions as execution progresses. These identities routinely operate in just-in-time modes that exceed static least-privilege constraints by design, crossing multiple administrative and security boundaries within a single execution.

At the same time, cloud platforms such as AWS, GCP, and Azure provide unprecedented visibility into NHI behavior. Fine-grained audit logs, identity graph APIs, and real-time permission

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tracing expose complete execution paths and privilege transitions at scale. This observability enables comprehensive reconstruction of identity interactions but also reveals a level of structural complexity that overwhelms existing analysis and review methodologies.

1.2 Shapeshifting Identities and Closed-Loop Escalation

Analysis of cloud IAM telemetry shows that privilege escalation for mission-critical NHIs tends to follow *closed-loop* patterns rather than linear progressions. These *shapeshifting identities* cyclically transition through multiple privilege states as part of normal operation, dynamically assuming and relinquishing roles across workflow stages. Such behavior represents a distinct operational security pattern that has not been systematically characterized.

While adversarial privilege cycles—such as lateral movement and attack graphs—are well studied, the cycles observed in IaC-driven workflows arise from legitimate orchestration logic and just-in-time permission acquisition:

A CI/CD pipeline assumes role A (deployment permissions) → triggers role B (testing environment access) → invokes role C (artifact signing) → returns to role A for the next deployment iteration.

These stable, recurring operational patterns induce strongly connected components (SCCs) in the privilege graph, defeat traditional DAG-based analysis, and motivate the need for structured classification rather than path-based reasoning.

1.3 Contribution

This work makes the following contributions:

- We characterize *operational privilege cycles* arising from IaC and CI/CD-driven workflows as a class distinct from adversarial attack graphs, providing empirical evidence of their prevalence, short-cycle structure, and stability across executions.
- We introduce a canonical, decodable representation for strongly connected components that captures cyclic privilege structure while tolerating bounded collisions, and show how it can be used as a primitive for scalable and explainable analysis of non-human identity permissions.
- We formalize an automated classification framework that maps cyclic privilege patterns into three actionable outcomes: *reduction* (provably benign cycles that can be collapsed), *fusion* (structurally equivalent cycles that share a single analyst decision), and *fusion–reduction* (approximate variants that can be jointly reviewed and simplified).
- We evaluate the proposed approach on a first limited set of real-world cloud IAM graph extracts, suggesting substantial reductions in the number of strongly connected components requiring manual review while preserving auditability and operational intent.

1.4 Organization

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows:

- Section 2 introduces automated evaluation of non-human identity permissions using DAG-based reasoning and linear temporal logic, and discusses why these approaches break down in the presence of strongly connected components.
- Section 3 presents the primordial invariant and its properties.

- Section 4 describes how the invariant is used to support automated SCC risk evaluation through reduction, fusion, and fusion–reduction operations.
- Section 5 identifies limitations in our current approach.
- Finally, Section 6 reviews background and related work.

2 Automated Evaluation of NHI Permissions

To gain understanding of the evolution of NHIs rights assignment, we build a temporal graph of their role assignments.

These temporal graphs are extremely simple for traditional service accounts: they often resolve to a single vertex denoting a single, static set of assignments: we can see them as a degenerated form of Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAG). Beyond that simple case, modern provisioners rely on staged deployment parking service accounts into temporary roles, or to versioned provisioning, leading to DAGs. Finally, complex IAM orchestrators may perform Just In Time role assignments, leading to cycling graphs.

To automate evaluation of temporal permission graphs, one must therefore make the distinction between acyclic and cyclic subgraphs.

2.1 Privilege Scoring

The methods in this paper require a scalar representation of the total privilege level assigned to each identity. We use the WAR (Write-Action-Read) norm[9], which maps consolidated Azure RBAC Control Plane assignments to positive integers based on three permission tiers: write operations (highest weight), action operations, and read operations (lowest weight) across different scope levels (Tenant, Management Group, Subscription, ...)

For the purposes of this paper, the specific scoring function is not critical: any monotonic privilege metric s that distinguishes escalation from de-escalation suffices. The invariant construction requires only that we can determine, for any temporally oriented edge (v_i, v_j) , whether $s_i < s_j$ (escalation), $s_i = s_j$ (flat), or $s_i > s_j$ (de-escalation).

All guarantees in this work assume a stable, monotonic privilege ordering function. Changes to the scalar semantics intentionally produce invariant drift, signaling a change in security interpretation rather than a structural change.

2.2 Directed Acyclic Graphs

Modern cloud security increasingly relies on automated policy-as-code IAM enforcement using formal methods. Linear Temporal Logic (LTL) naturally expresses security properties for directed acyclic privilege flows: suppose we capture the privilege level of a NHI in Azure using the WAR norm. Since the value of WAR is a scalar s , we can express a privilege escalation with a simple atomic proposition:

$$\text{inc} \equiv s_{t+1} > s_t$$

There are many ways to assess and to enforce privilege escalation policies using LTL and scalar risk levels. For example, we can express the temporal requirement that a peak privilege escalation point exists after which no more escalation occurs using a clause with standard LTL quantifiers **F** (eventually) and **G** (always):

$$FG\neg inc$$

This property is verified using a Büchi automaton (Figure 1):

Figure 1: Büchi automaton for $FG\neg inc$. The accepting state q_1 (double circle) represents “no more increases forever.” An infinite run is accepted if it visits q_1 infinitely often *and* stays there (no inc transitions).

2.2.1 Scaling Considerations

Policy-as-code transforms LTL expressions into security enforcements; once scalar thresholds have been set, it enables temporal drift detection. Large corporations routinely handle thousands of NHIs, if not more, and policy checks can be compute intensive. In the Public Cloud, grouping NHIs into fibers[3] can achieve significant compression rates (up to 1:25 as we’ve measured experimentally[4]): policy-as-code benefits from this grouping, because the WAR norm is preserved through fibration.

Another powerful property of WAR one can leverage on to further optimize policy-as-code is that the induced distance $d_\kappa()$ defines nested interpretation scales[9]: suppose two fibers f_1 and f_2 stand $d_\kappa(f_1, f_2)$ apart. Depending on the level of risk tolerance one can afford, it is possible to group these two unrelated fibers into equivalence bands:

- if $d_\kappa(f_1, f_2) = 0$, both fibers have identical WAR norms and may be grouped into the same equivalence class
- if $d_\kappa(f_1, f_2) < 10$, both fibers have similar privilege levels up to read permissions. They may be grouped into a slightly coarser equivalence class
- if $d_\kappa(f_1, f_2) < 100$, both fibers have similar privilege levels up to read and action permissions. They may be grouped into an even coarser equivalence class

Altogether, the use of fibration and equivalence bands greatly optimizes processing temporal evolution of large NHI populations in Azure.

2.3 Cycles

Our approach to SCCs management is not to make LTL work for cycles, but to use LTL as a filter inside a larger security semantics.

The intuition is this: whenever we encounter a SCC, call an oracle to transform it in three possible ways:

- If the SCC is simple enough, **reduce** it into a degenerated, one vertex component. Replace the whole SCC by this single vertex in the permissions graph, and proceed LTL as usual.
- If the SCC is slightly more complex, **fuse-reduce** it into a degenerated, two-vertices oscillator. Replace the whole SCC by this oscillator in the permissions graph, and proceed LTL forking (for example) two branches.
- Otherwise, attempt **fuse** it with another well-understood SCC using a pattern-matching mechanism. If the match belongs to a whitelist, the oracle returns True. Otherwise it returns False. Replace the whole SCC by this boolean assertion, and proceed LTL as usual (immediate policy violation if the oracle returns False).

We now proceed to the formalization of our oracle, a construct we call the primorial invariant.

3 The Primorial Invariant

3.1 Definition

Given a strongly connected component $G = (V, E)$ with vertex scalar labels $v_i \in \mathbb{R}$:

Primorial invariant: Encodes both edge directionality and vertex scalar value progression (increasing/decreasing/flat) using the *primorial* ($P_n = \prod_{j=0}^{n-1} p_j$) to separate small primes from big primes. Named for the primorial construction that enables disjoint prime ranges.

We use the term invariant in an operational sense: equality of invariants implies equivalence under a defined security semantics, not graph isomorphism.

Throughout this paper, “R” refers to the value of the primorial invariant for a given identity or fiber.

3.2 Calculation

R is computed as follows:

1. Enumerate all elementary cycles C_1, \dots, C_k of G (using Johnson’s algorithm).
2. Determine orientation O_i of each cycle C_i . If all edges are bidirectional, the cycle is unoriented: pick an orientation at random and mark the cycle as unoriented.
3. For each oriented rotation k of each cycle $C_i = (v_0, v_1, \dots, v_{n-1}, v_0)$ with n edges, compute the rational invariant $r_{i,k}$ as follows:
 - (a) Let p_j denote the j -th prime ($p_0 = 2, p_1 = 3, p_2 = 5, \dots$).
 - (b) Compute the primorial $P_n = \prod_{j=0}^{n-1} p_j$.
 - (c) Let q_0 be the smallest prime greater than P_n , and define $q_{j+1} = \text{next_prime}(q_j)$ for $j \geq 0$.
 - (d) Initialize $r_i = 1$.
 - (e) For each edge e_j from vertex v_j (value s_j) to v_{j+1} (value s_{j+1}), multiply $r_{i,k}$ by:
 - If e_j is **bidirectional** (i.e. backtracking) and the cycle is oriented:

- 1 if $s_j = s_{j+1}$,
- $\frac{q_j}{p_j}$ if $s_j < s_{j+1}$,
- $\frac{1}{p_j \cdot q_j}$ if $s_j > s_{j+1}$.
- If e_j is **bidirectional** and the cycle is unoriented:
 - 1 if $s_j = s_{j+1}$,
 - 0 if $s_j \neq s_{j+1}$. (force exit the loops in this case)
- If e_j is **directed**:
 - $\frac{1}{p_j}$ if $s_j = s_{j+1}$,
 - q_j if $s_j < s_{j+1}$,
 - $\frac{1}{p_j \cdot q_j^2}$ if $s_j > s_{j+1}$.

Set the rational invariant of cycle C_i as $r_i = \min(r_{i,k})$. It is a rational number uniquely encoding the cycle’s vertex value progression and edge directionality.

4. Construct the vector $\mathbf{R} = (r_1, \dots, r_i)$.
5. Sort the vector in ascending order to yield a deterministic representation.

Note: Although r_i is represented as a rational number, it is not used as a numeric metric. The invariant is a symbolic encoding of cycle structure and privilege transitions. Arithmetic reduction or normalization of the rational form would destroy semantic information carried by prime factor multiplicities and is therefore intentionally avoided. Equality and comparison of invariants are defined at the level of exact factor structure, not numeric value.

3.2.1 Properties

The dimension of \mathbf{R} depends on the number of elementary cycles, capped at a maximum n_{cycles} . We intentionally bound cycle length, as longer cycles in temporal IAM graphs predominantly reflect permission churn and snapshot artifacts rather than meaningful operational behavior.

For oriented cycles, the algorithm produces factors according to 6 possible edge types:

Edge Type	Factor	p_j in <i>Denominator</i>	q_j in <i>Numerator</i>	q_j in <i>Denominator</i>
Directed, flat	$1/p_j$	1	0	0
Directed, increasing	q_j	0	1	0
Directed, decreasing	$1/(p_j \cdot q_j^2)$	1	0	2
Bidirectional, flat	1	0	0	0
Bidirectional, increasing	q_j/p_j	1	1	0
Bidirectional, decreasing	$1/(p_j \cdot q_j)$	1	0	1

Table 1: Mapping edge types with factors

Each edge type (except bidirectional flat) produces a unique exponent signature (e_p, e_N, e_D) for the triple (p_j in D , q_j in N , q_j in D).

- **Discrimination:** By design, all fully bidirectional elementary cycles share the same invariant $R = 1$ when scalars are constant, $R = 0$ otherwise. All other elementary cycles exhibit invariants $R \neq 1, R \neq 0$.

- **Cycles are collision-free:** Oriented cycles with distinct edge-type sequences map to distinct R values (Theorem 1).
- **Cycles reversibility:** given a fraction $R = a/b$ (in unreduced form), we can infer cycle length (if unoriented), then decode the sequence of edge types.
- **Deterministic:** Sorting ensures permutation independence of cycles.
- **Scalar-aware:** Vertex scalar values influence the invariant, unlike pure adjacency-based fingerprints.
- **Variable-length:** The vector dimension encodes the number of cycles, giving structural information.
- **Rational:** By construction, $\mathbf{R} \in (\mathbb{Q}^+)^n$. These rationals function as symbolic identifiers rather than numeric quantities.

We now establish two key properties: cycle-level collision-freeness and cycles reversibility.

Theorem 1 (Cycle-level collision-freeness). *Let C and C' be two oriented elementary cycles of the same length n , with respective edge-type sequences $\sigma = (t_0, \dots, t_{n-1})$ and $\sigma' = (t'_0, \dots, t'_{n-1})$ after rotation-minimization. If $\sigma \neq \sigma'$, then $r(C) \neq r(C')$.*

Proof. The invariant for cycle C is the product $r(C) = \prod_{j=0}^{n-1} f(t_j, j)$, where $f(t_j, j)$ is the factor assigned to edge type t_j at position j .

Step 1: Positional encoding via disjoint prime ranges. By construction, position j uses two primes: p_j (the j -th prime, with $p_j \leq p_{n-1}$) and q_j (the j -th prime strictly above the primorial $P_n = \prod_{i=0}^{n-1} p_i$). Since $q_j > P_n \geq p_i$ for all $i < n$, the sets $\{p_0, \dots, p_{n-1}\}$ and $\{q_0, \dots, q_{n-1}\}$ are disjoint. Moreover, all $2n$ primes are distinct.

Step 2: Injectivity at each position. At position j , the five non-trivial edge types produce the following prime signatures in the factorization of $r(C)$, written as (e_{p_j}, e_{q_j}) where e_{p_j} is the exponent of p_j in the denominator and e_{q_j} is the signed exponent of q_j (positive = numerator, negative = denominator):

Edge type	e_{p_j}	e_{q_j}
Directed, flat	1	0
Directed, increasing	0	+1
Directed, decreasing	1	-2
Bidirectional, increasing	1	+1
Bidirectional, decreasing	1	-1

All five pairs (e_{p_j}, e_{q_j}) are distinct. Bidirectional flat contributes $(0, 0)$, which is a sixth distinct pair. Therefore $f(t_j, j) \neq f(t'_j, j)$ whenever $t_j \neq t'_j$.

Step 3: Independence across positions. Since p_j and q_j are unique to position j , the exponents contributed by position j do not interact with those of any other position $j' \neq j$ in the prime factorization of $r(C)$. By the fundamental theorem of arithmetic, the factorization of $r(C)$ (as an unreduced fraction) uniquely determines each pair (e_{p_j}, e_{q_j}) for $j = 0, \dots, n-1$, hence the full edge-type sequence σ .

Therefore $\sigma \neq \sigma'$ implies distinct factorizations, hence $r(C) \neq r(C')$. □

Corollary 1. *Cycles of different lengths $n \neq n'$ also cannot collide: the primordial P_n changes with n , shifting the q_j range. In particular, q_0 for length n differs from q_0 for length n' , so the factorizations involve different primes entirely and are trivially distinct.*

3.2.2 SCC and cycle collisions

In this work, the term *SCC collision* refers to the case where two non-isomorphic SCC topologies map to the same R -vector, whereas *cycle collision* refers to the case where two non-isomorphic cycle topologies map to the same R -scalar. While SCC collisions do happen in practice, one must stress out that, when looked at the individual cycle level, collision pairs contain the same multiset of cycle signatures. From a security perspective, what matters is not the precise graph topology, but the privilege escalation paths it enables. Two SCCs with identical cycle signatures have identical security properties at the cycle level—they represent the same attack surface.

Thus, what appears as a “collision” from a graph-theoretic perspective is actually *correct behavior*: the invariant is grouping SCCs by their security-relevant structure, abstracting away topological details that do not affect privilege flow analysis.

Absolute vs. Relative Privilege. The R -values encode *relative* privilege relationships (which vertices are higher or lower along each cycle), not *absolute* privilege levels. Two cycles with identical R -values might traverse different absolute WAR levels—for instance, an Admin \leftrightarrow Root cycle versus a User \leftrightarrow PowerUser cycle could have the same R -value despite different severity. However, this absolute information is captured separately by the WAR delta between cycle endpoints, which is tracked independently in the analysis. The R -invariant and WAR delta together provide complete cycle-level characterization.

Adversarial Scope. Our threat model addresses operational complexity rather than adversarial manipulation of the privilege graph. We assume the IAM control plane is trusted; an attacker with write access to role assignments operates outside our scope.

3.2.3 Reversibility

For $R \neq \mathbf{1}$ and $R \neq \mathbf{0}$, cycles-level reversibility is illustrated by providing a decoding algorithm. The following algorithm exploits the disjoint prime ranges and the fundamental theorem of arithmetic, which guarantees uniqueness of prime factorization for unreduced rational numbers:

Given R :

1. Factor N and D into prime factorizations, infer cycle length n
2. For each $j \in \{0, \dots, n-1\}$, compute p_j (the j -th prime) and q_j (starting from the first prime after *primorial*(p_{n-1}))
3. Extract exponents from the factorization and look up the edge type in the table

This produces a unique sequence $\sigma = (t_0, t_1, \dots, t_{n-1})$ of edge types for any elementary cycle.

Note that a full SCC is of course not reversible given its invariant, because the relative topology of individual elementary cycles constituting the SCC is not encoded into R .

All guarantees in this paper are relative to the assumed privilege semantics (scalar WAR values, directed/bidirectional transitions, and bounded SCC size). We do not claim adversarial robustness or universal graph uniqueness; instead, the invariant is designed as a deterministic abstraction for scalable policy review.

4 Use of the Invariant For Automated SCC Risks Evaluation

4.1 Reduction

The invariant value $R = \mathbf{1}_n$ arises exclusively when an SCC is fully bidirectional and all vertices share identical WAR scalars. In this degenerate configuration, every elementary cycle traverses only bidirectional edges between privilege-equivalent vertices, yielding the trivial product of unit factors.

This singularity has implications for security: when $R = \mathbf{1}_n$, all vertices within the SCC are indistinguishable from a privilege standpoint. No path induces a net privilege change under the WAR-based semantics. The SCC represents a cluster of mutually interchangeable identities.

Consequently, the entire SCC can be reduced to a single representative vertex bearing the common WAR score. No privilege-relevant distinctions are lost under this abstraction: remediating the representative remediates the class, and any security assertion about one vertex holds for all.

The discriminating nature of R ensures that $R = \mathbf{1}_n$ is a stable characterization: any perturbation that breaks the degeneracy (adding a directed edge, or introducing WAR variation) immediately shifts the invariant away from unity, signaling that reduction is no longer valid.

4.2 Fusion (Directed topologies)

Definition 1 (Fusion equivalence). *Let G_1 and G_2 be two SCCs with sorted invariant vectors $\mathbf{R}_1 = (r_1^{(1)}, \dots, r_k^{(1)})$ and $\mathbf{R}_2 = (r_1^{(2)}, \dots, r_m^{(2)})$ respectively, where both contain at least one directed edge (i.e., $\mathbf{R} \neq \mathbf{1}_n$ and $\mathbf{R} \neq \mathbf{0}_n$). We say G_1 and G_2 are fusion-equivalent, written $G_1 \sim_F G_2$, if and only if:*

1. $k = m$ (same number of elementary cycles), and
2. $r_i^{(1)} = r_i^{(2)}$ for all $i \in \{1, \dots, k\}$ (componentwise equality of sorted invariants).

That is, $G_1 \sim_F G_2$ iff $\mathbf{R}_1 = \mathbf{R}_2$ as sorted tuples of rationals. A fusion group is an equivalence class under \sim_F .

Sorting the invariant vector ensures that \sim_F is independent of the order in which Johnson's algorithm enumerates elementary cycles. Two SCCs with the same multiset of cycle invariants are fused regardless of internal cycle ordering.

When an SCC contains at least one directed edge, its invariant \mathbf{R} necessarily departs from both the reduction signature ($\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{1}_n$) and the oscillator signature that we will explain momentarily. Directed edges introduce asymmetric factors q_j for privilege escalation ($s < s'$), $\frac{1}{p_j q_j^2}$ for de-escalation ($s > s'$) that leave indelible traces in the prime factorization of each component r_i .

These traces encode genuine topological structure: the pattern of escalation and de-escalation transitions across elementary cycles. By Theorem 1, each cycle invariant r_i uniquely determines the edge-type sequence of the corresponding cycle. Consequently, two SCCs in the same fusion group share identical multisets of cycle-level escalation profiles, hence equivalent security risk.

This equivalence motivates fusion: grouping SCCs by their \mathbf{R} vectors rather than analyzing each individually. At initial assessment (t_0), an organization may face thousands of SCCs: an intractable review burden. Fusion compresses this to a manageable set of distinct escalation signatures, each representing a class of security-equivalent topologies awaiting approval or remediation.

Unlike reduction, fusion preserves the full vertex structure within each SCC. The compression operates at the pattern level: human reviewers approve or flag escalation signatures, while automated monitoring ensures no SCC drifts into an unapproved signature class.

R classifies SCCs so that structurally distinct SCCs sharing the same signature pose equivalent threats and conversely, that a signature change signals a genuine topological evolution warranting re-evaluation.

4.2.1 Shallow Temporal Evolution

Consider two shallow SCCs observed at different epochs with no common fibers, hence no common roles:

- **Epoch t_1 :** SCC_A with 3 fiber vertices $[f_1, f_2, f_3]$, 3 elementary cycles, $R_A = [r_1, r_2, r_3]$
- **Epoch t_2 :** SCC_B with 3 fiber vertices $[f_4, f_5, f_6]$, 3 elementary cycles, $R_B = [r_1, r_2, r_3]$

Despite sharing *zero common roles*, the three components of R_B match R_A exactly. This reveals:

1. The original 3-cycle privilege structure from Epoch t_1 persists in Epoch t_2
2. Both SCCs originate from the same deployment factory/IaC orchestrator, despite complete role changes

4.2.2 Deeper Temporal Evolution

Our investigations show that shapeshifting NHIs follow multi-scale evolution patterns: they feature shallow SCCs (typically 2-3 periods) included into deeper temporal structures.

Comparing SCCs across different temporal depths provides:

- **Collision resolution:** SCCs that produce identical short-period invariants can be distinguished by evolution history
- **Operational lineage discovery:** Identify which NHI groups descend from common IaC templates/orchestration patterns
- **Factory grouping:** Group identities by deployment source without requiring role matching or metadata correlation

The example below is a side-by-side comparison of two actual NHI groups associated to shallow SCCs fused by invariant matching. Both groups share a partial set of Azure roles at short term: the difference, exhibited by 2 different fibers, is highlighted in orange and green in their corresponding SCCs:

Figure 2: Two NHI groups sharing the same SCC invariants at short temporal depth

They turn out to match also exactly at deeper temporal depth:

Figure 3: The NHIs are still sharing same SCC invariants over a time span

4.2.3 Fusion-Reduction (Oscillators)

When an SCC is fully bidirectional yet exhibits non-constant WAR scalars, its invariant satisfies $R = \mathbf{0}_n$ without retaining a distinctive prime structure: this arises intentionally, because unoriented cycles employ factor 0 for edges connecting vertices of differing WAR values.

The oscillator signature admits a powerful simplification: since all edges are bidirectional, privilege can flow freely in either direction between any pair of vertices. The security-relevant information reduces to the amplitude of privilege oscillation, the range between minimum and maximum WAR values within the SCC.

Consequently, any fully bidirectional SCC with non-constant scalar can be safely collapsed into a canonical two-vertex oscillator: one vertex bearing s_{min} , the other s_{max} , connected by a single bidirectional edge. This fusion-reduction preserves the essential security semantics (the privilege swing) while discarding the irrelevant intermediate topology.

Figure 4: Two SCCs with identical R -vectors but distinct topologies can be fused-reduced into the same oscillator (+/- denote privilege increase/decrease)

Unlike full reduction where all vertices are equivalent, fusion-reduction acknowledges that privilege does vary, but the variation is symmetric and fully reversible along any path.

4.3 Initial Experimental Results

4.3.1 Sample dataset

Given the difficulty to gather large amounts of confidential representative datasets as part of this research, we were constrained to reason on a limited initial sample of shapeshifting NHIs analyzed over a period of 11 days, backward from January 05, 2026, in a small set of Azure Tenants. The SCCs were identified using Tarjan’s algorithm on directed graphs constructed from daily Entra ID snapshots. Cycles were identified using Johnson’s classical algorithm within less than a minute of CPU time on a standard VM.

Metric	Value
Total unique NHIs	11,842
NHIs participating in SCCs	449
Total SCCs analyzed	297
Total privilege cycles	1,161

Table 2: Summary statistics of the analyzed IAM dataset

4.3.2 Cycle enumeration complexity

A potential concern with Johnson’s algorithm is its worst-case exponential complexity in the number of elementary cycles. The following tables show that, in practice, operational IAM graphs produce small SCCs with few short cycles, keeping enumeration tractable.

Cycles per SCC	Count	Percentage
1	119	40.1%
2	8	2.7%
3	1	0.3%
4	57	19.2%
5	5	1.7%
6	10	3.4%
7	87	29.3%
8	3	1.0%
10	5	1.7%
13	1	0.3%
14	1	0.3%

Table 3: Distribution of elementary cycle counts per SCC

Cycle length	Count	Percentage
2	918	79.1%
3	172	14.8%
4	65	5.6%
5	6	0.5%
Total	1,161	

Table 4: Distribution of elementary cycle lengths

The maximum observed cycle length is 5, and 93.9% of cycles have length 2 or 3. The maximum number of elementary cycles in any single SCC is 14. These characteristics confirm that Johnson’s algorithm operates well within its efficient regime for operational IAM graphs: the short-cycle, small-SCC structure that arises from IaC workflows avoids the combinatorial explosion that would affect dense, large-diameter graphs.

4.3.3 Compression Results

Invariant category	SCCs	Groups	Compression
Reductions (R=1)	179	8	22.3×
Oscillators (R=0)	7	3	2.3×
Fusions	111	40	2.8×

Table 5: Compression results by R category

4.3.4 Discussion

The results demonstrate that the majority of SCCs observed in production IAM graphs correspond to a small number of recurring operational patterns. Of the 179 SCCs classified as reductions,

only eight distinct signatures were identified. These SCCs are characterized by fully bidirectional transitions between WAR-equivalent states ($R = 1$), indicating credentials that repeatedly return to the same effective privilege. From an operational perspective, these cycles represent structural noise rather than meaningful privilege flow; a single approval or policy review suffices to cover all instances in the group.

Oscillators form a much smaller class. Seven SCCs reduce to three signatures, each corresponding to bounded oscillation between minimum and maximum WAR states. While these cycles involve privilege change, the transitions are predictable and constrained. As such, they require understanding of only a few canonical patterns rather than per-instance inspection.

Fusions account for the most semantically interesting category. 111 SCCs compress to forty distinct groups, each defined by identical R -vectors capturing directed privilege flow topology. Unlike reductions and oscillators, fusions represent genuine credential movement through privilege states. These SCCs warrant deeper investigation, but the invariant ensures that structurally identical cases are analyzed once rather than repeatedly.

SCC Size	Count	Dominant Operation
2 vertices	113	Reduction (95%)
≥ 3 vertices	111	Fusion (62%)

Table 6: SCC size distribution and dominant cycle operation

The distinction between trivial and non-trivial cycles is further supported by SCC size. Among two-vertex SCCs, 95% are reductions, indicating bidirectional chatter between equivalent states. In contrast, SCCs with three or more vertices are dominated by fusions (62%), confirming that larger SCCs correspond to directed operational workflows rather than noise.

Overall, the primordial invariant reduces 297 SCCs to 51 unique signatures. This compression transforms manual triage into structured pattern review, while remaining analytically defined rather than data-driven. The invariant preserves behavioral semantics necessary for security analysis, while enabling scalability in large cloud environments.

4.3.5 Further Optimization

A promising avenue that we mentioned in paragraph 2.2.1 but haven't leveraged in our research is the opportunity to improve fusion efficiency by merging fusion groups into equivalence bands, the bandwidth being directly dependent on the level of risk tolerance we can afford. We leave that investigation for potential future work.

5 Limitations

Our domain specifically targets short-cycle NHI privilege graphs with well-defined characteristics:

- Scope: Azure Control Plane role assignments to NHI principals (SPNs, Managed Identities) forming temporal cycles.
- Scalar IAM scoring: NHI RBAC privileges scored using a scalar.
- Compression (optional, but highly recommended): NHIs grouping by fibration.

- Temporal resolution: Roles changes are not captured on-the-fly using an event-driven architecture. Instead, we are relying on daily snapshots, this may cause artifacts in the construction of cycles.

Note that the experimental dataset is small and should be enriched with more diverse sources, from multiple Cloud providers and organizations, to get a more accurate assessment of the benefits.

6 Background and Related Work

6.1 Policy-as-Code and Formal Verification in IAM

Modern cloud IAM increasingly relies on **policy-as-code** frameworks for automated enforcement:

1. Open Policy Agent[1]: General-purpose policy engine using Rego language for declarative access control
2. AWS Cedar[2]: Authorization policy language with formal semantics and SMT-based verification
3. IAM As Code[5, 11]: Infrastructure-as-code declarations with static analysis
4. AWS IAM Access Analyzer[6], Azure Policy[7]: Continuous compliance checking via event-driven policies

These frameworks work well for stateless policies (“deny admin access from untrusted IPs”) and acyclic workflows (“deployment must follow staging \rightarrow canary \rightarrow production”). With SCCs in the privilege graph, these tools struggle with fluctuating permissions.

Existing IAM research and open-source tools[10, 12, 13] as well as the major CNAPP and CIEM tools address adversarial lateral movement through attack graphs, which exhibit long, complex privilege escalation chains with high efficiency.

However, the security literature has not systematically characterized *operational cycle patterns* that emerge from legitimate IaC workflow structure rather than adversarial behavior.

Existing methods lack:

- fingerprinting for distinguishing operational cycles from policy violations,
- enabling pattern-based classification at scale,
- integration with formal verification frameworks. Current practice treats anomalies as potential attacks, forcing manual case-by-case review.

6.2 Graph Invariants

Computing a provably unique fingerprint for arbitrary graphs requires canonical graph labeling, a problem at least as hard as graph isomorphism and believed to be computationally intractable in the general case[8]. Any fingerprinting method faces a fundamental tradeoff:

1. **Perfect uniqueness:** Requires exponential-time enumeration of vertex permutations or solving canonical form problems

2. **Practical efficiency:** Accept potential collisions (multiset ordering ambiguity) in exchange for polynomial-time computation

Classical graph invariants provide low collision fingerprints but fail to capture the semantics needed for NHI security:

- **Ihara zeta functions** list the basic cycles in a graph and summarize the structure of strongly connected components, but they don't consider backtracking edges, which are important for understanding the actual behavior of identities in a security setting.
- **Spectral invariants**, which are based on a graph's overall connectivity, are helpful for understanding broad structural properties but fail to capture the detailed patterns of cycles or the specific behaviors within the network.

Modern graph fingerprinting methods achieve high discrimination (almost zero collisions):

- **Graph Neural Networks (GNNs)** learn embeddings in \mathbb{R}^{128} through message passing. While they achieve state-of-the-art performance on benchmark tasks, they are black-box models and arguably excessive for analyzing small SCCs. The learning process (including message passing, gradient descent, and embedding optimization) is computationally intensive and offers little additional discriminative power compared to simpler approaches, such as prime-factorization-based invariants.
- **Weisfeiler-Leman (WL) refinement** iteratively updates vertex labels using neighborhood hashing, producing fast fingerprints for SCCs of all sizes. Although WL could be adapted to handle scalar increases or decreases, it does not do so natively. Moreover, the method provides limited interpretability, making it harder to explain the results in a security context.

7 Conclusion

Modern Infrastructure-as-Code has introduced shapeshifting identities: credentials that cyclically transition through privilege states during operational workflows. These transitions form strongly connected components (SCCs) in privilege graphs, which are challenging to analyze using traditional Linear Temporal Logic methods and require manual classification. In production systems with hundreds of distinct SCCs, scalable fingerprinting becomes essential.

In this work, we introduced a rational-number encoding for privilege cycles that captures both the topology and behavioral semantics of SCCs. This approach enables automated classification of cycles into three categories, simplifying what previously required labor-intensive review.

The primordial invariant provides a practical foundation for cycle-based IAM security in cloud environments, particularly where operational privilege patterns follow short cycles. By enabling automated, pattern-based classification of shapeshifting identities, our method supports scalable security analysis and improves the reliability of cloud orchestration. These techniques lay the groundwork for more systematic, explainable, and efficient management of cloud privileges in modern infrastructure.

Appendix: a Worked Example of Invariant Calculation

Consider a minimal SCC with 4 vertices forming two overlapping elementary cycles:

Graph Structure:

- Vertices: $\{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ with values $\{5, 10, 15, 15\}$
- Edges: $(0 \rightarrow 1)$, $(1 \rightarrow 2)$, $(2 \rightarrow 0)$, $(2 \rightarrow 3)$, $(3 \rightarrow 1)$ (all directed)

Elementary Cycles:

1. $C_1 = [0, 1, 2, 0]$: Triangle with 3 edges
2. $C_2 = [1, 2, 3, 1]$: Triangle with 3 edges, sharing vertices 1 and 2 with C_1

Invariant Calculation for C_1 (triangle $0 \rightarrow 1 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 0$):

- $n = 3$ edges, so $P_3 = 2 \times 3 \times 5 = 30$
- $q_0 = 31$ (next prime after 30), $q_1 = 37$, $q_2 = 41$
- Edge 0 ($0 \rightarrow 1$): $5 < 10$, directed, increasing \Rightarrow op=I, factor = $q_0 = 31$
- $r = 1 \times 31 = 31$
- Edge 1 ($1 \rightarrow 2$): $10 < 15$, directed, increasing \Rightarrow op=I, factor = $q_1 = 37$
- $r = 31 \times 37 = 1147$
- Edge 2 ($2 \rightarrow 0$): $15 > 5$, directed, decreasing \Rightarrow op=D, factor = $\frac{1}{p_2 \cdot q_2^2} = \frac{1}{5 \times 41^2} = \frac{1}{8405}$
- $r = 1147 \times \frac{1}{8405} = \frac{1147}{8405}$

Result: $r_1 = \frac{1147}{8405} \approx 0.1364$

Invariant Calculation for C_2 (triangle $1 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 3 \rightarrow 1$):

- $n = 3$ edges, so $P_3 = 2 \times 3 \times 5 = 30$
- $q_0 = 31$, $q_1 = 37$, $q_2 = 41$
- Edge 0 ($1 \rightarrow 2$): $10 < 15$, directed, increasing \Rightarrow op=I, factor = $q_0 = 31$
- $r = 1 \times 31 = 31$
- Edge 1 ($2 \rightarrow 3$): $15 = 15$, directed, flat \Rightarrow op=F, factor = $\frac{1}{p_1} = \frac{1}{3}$
- $r = 31 \times \frac{1}{3} = \frac{31}{3}$
- Edge 2 ($3 \rightarrow 1$): $15 > 10$, directed, decreasing \Rightarrow op=D, factor = $\frac{1}{p_2 \cdot q_2^2} = \frac{1}{5 \times 41^2} = \frac{1}{8405}$
- $r = \frac{31}{3} \times \frac{1}{8405} = \frac{31}{25215}$

Result: $r_2 = \frac{31}{25215} \approx 0.00123$

Final invariant vector (sorted in ascending order): $\mathbf{R} = \left(\frac{31}{25215}, \frac{1147}{8405}\right) \approx (0.00123, 0.1364)$.

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